

Publication date : 25 Août 2023
DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.8280640

Eschapsology

Synthesis of the emergence of a middle discipline between science and theology.

AUTHOR: OUAFAE LAMRAOUI

ENGLISH VERSION

SUMMARY

Knowledge is a common and universal intellectual good where each individual work is a contribution to the collective knowledge of humanity. Founding a median discipline that offers new perspectives to both of science and theology involves the construction of a theoretical framework and its own methodology. The intellectual progress consists in extracting the key to science with the scientific method by translating the idiom of the Book through physical phenomena corresponding sufficiently so that the application of their laws describes and models the object of study with relevance. The production of the physical model resulting from this process marks the development of a new scientific theory based on manuscripts and the history of the Book as empirical evidence.

Ancient philosophy & natural sciences

In the 7th century BC, many philosophical schools emerged with the first thinkers focused on the observation of nature. The term *philosophy*, which appears from antiquity in semantic construction, is then a derivative of ancient Greek [philosophia - φιλοσοφία] which literally means « the love of wisdom » in the sense of knowledge. It is composed of the verb to love [phileo - φιλέω] and [sophia - σοφία] which translates wisdom and knowledge. Wisdom is a faculty relating to intelligence, common sense, science and philosophy. It is a term generally used to designate the virtues of a person who is reasonable and moderate in his desires. The sage acquires through wisdom a fair and thoughtful conduct in his judgments. Of irreproachable morals, the first sages were able to observe the world around them with an individual philosophical view tending to keep a disciplined and reasonable behavior far from all excesses. Their fields of study are inspired by various disciplines whose primary objective is a quest for truth.

This ancient period of the first dissemination of knowledge spans on several centuries marks a turning point. The first philosophical schools called pre-Socratic, were the result of collective projects formed around a philosopher. Three of them are nevertheless decisive in modern science: The Milesian School, founded by **Thales** (625-548 BC) one of the Seven sages of ancient Greece, produced the first ideas on astronomy, biology, cosmology, geometry and rational concepts of physics ; the Pythagorean School, a philosophical, scientific and religious brotherhood was formed by **Pythagoras** (580-495 BC) founder of Greek mathematics ; and the Atomist School, founded by **Leucippus** (500-420 BC) and his disciple **Democritus** (460-390 BC), whom proposed a materialist physical theory conceptualizing a universe composed of vacuum and microscopic elements of matter called [atoms - ἄτομα].

The modern distinction between philosophy and science traces its design when it participates in the golden age of Greece. Western philosophy is then deeply marked by three philosophers, including **Socrates** (470-399 BC) whom breaks with the Greek mythological thought of his time, initiates the method of critical and rational reflection extended to all

knowledge. Even if he did not leave any writings during his lifetime, his disciple **Plato** (427-348 BC) developed philosophical conceptions with his theory of intelligible forms (or theory of ideas) which opposed dualities of two visions of the world. One of these visions appears in the visible form of things independently of the other attainable only by the intellect which conceptualizes the idea of things. His allegory of the cave is a metaphysical digest through which he traces the process of access to knowledge, passing from the sphere of the sensible world to the intelligible world. He distinguishes between philosophers and theologians by formulating the "theology" term for the first time [1]. He founded the Academy of Plato in which he taught one of his disciples **Aristotle** (384-322 BC) whose doctrine is the antithesis of that of Plato whom he objects by one of his many works « *The Metaphysics* ». In his work, Aristotle distinguishes three theoretical philosophical branches: mathematics, physics and theology [2]. He develops the first reflections on the scientific method. The wide field of research that he tackled in various fields of knowledge and the philosophy he defined as the science of first principles influenced the thinkers and debates of medieval times.

Most of the ancient literature that testifies to the beliefs of its authors also reflects their desire to reform religion. This current of thought which flourished from the 4th century BC was also expressed, far from the classic themes of the Law, the alliance, the elect... in the poetic and sapiential books of the Old Testament. Written in Hebrew for the most part by anonymous authors, the corpus of the sages which consists of seven books: Book of Job (5th century BC); Proverbs (between the 6th and 4th centuries BC); Song of Songs (4th century BC); Psalms (-460 BC); Ecclesiastes (3rd century BC); Ecclesiasticus (-200 BC) and Wisdom of Solomon (written in Greek around the year 0), clarifies the ambiguity by differentiating human wisdom from Divine Wisdom. While secular wisdom is first described as a moral ideal consistent with the literature of the day, the corpus comes to elevate in degrees the sanctity of the Wisdom of God. The advent of the New Testament texts clearly marks the theological tangent taken by the Holy Scriptures. The editorial work undertaken by the Apostles and other disciples, notably John in his Gospel, tends to put a point of discernment between the very down to earth love [phileo - φιλέω] of profane wisdom embodied in the philosophical concept; and the higher love [agapao - ἀγαπᾶς] of Wisdom as an individual person animated by the Holy Spirit [3].

[1] **Platon** – *La République*, traduction & présentation by Georges Leroux, édition Flammarion, 2016. | References : théologie, book II 379a à 383c ; knowledge reasoning, book V 476e–480a ; visible reality and intelligible reality, book VI 509d–511e ; allegory of the cave, book VII.

[2] **Aristote** – *The Metaphysics* | References : theology, book A(I), 3, 983.b.29 & book B(III), 4, 1000.a.9-30 ; The three parts of the philosophy, book E(VI), 1, 1026a.

[3] [**Gospel of John 21:15-17**] Author's comment : *Témoignage, les mémoires de Sagesse (Testimony, the memories of Wisdom)* –

The era of theological debates

In the Middle Ages, as Christianity spread in the West and Islam in the East, the emergence of great reflections on the human condition characterized experimental descriptions of secular wisdom. Philosophy becomes a multidisciplinary field which aims at the rational knowledge of the world and of thought by including sciences such as physics, political philosophy, ethics and logic. The particularity of Islamic philosophy draws its sources both from the Quranic texts and the Sunnah, but also from the rationalist methods and reasoning of Greek thinkers such as Plato and Aristotle. Then it differentiates two philosophical currents: the doctrine of *falsafa* which claims to be pure Hellenistic philosophy; and the doctrine of the *kalam* which is based on Greek dialectics and rational argument. The latter is inspired, among other things, by the theory of atomism conceptualized by Leucippus and Democritus, to which applies a demonstrative reasoning of theological principles. Jews and Christians also adopt the concept of *kalam* which consists of debates by oppositions of ideas both interreligious and interdisciplinary.

In the 12th century, the thought of medieval scientific and philosophical brought out also the first critics of ancient philosophy. In writing their respective works « *The Intentions of the Philosophers* » and the « *Book of Argumentation in Defense of Despised Religion* », the Persian jurist **Al-Ghazali** (1058-1111) [4] criticizes contemporary Muslim philosophers like **Avicenna** (980-1037); and Rabbi **Judah Halevi** (1075-1141) [5] whom rejects philosophy, *kalam* and any form of rational theology, unwittingly produced a more favorable reaction to philosophy. In Andalusia, the debate between thinkers and religious came to end with the publication of the works of **Avempace** (1080-1139) [6] and **Averroès** (1126-1198) [7]. Of Neoplatonic inspiration, Avempace author of many works of mathematics, rejects the mysticism of Al-Ghazali and founds in his « *Farewell Letter* » his theory of the

immortality of the soul according that the the soul rises gradually in the intellectual rather than the spiritual. In turn, Averroes theologian and Muslim jurist allied to the doctrines of Aristotle, is inspired by the theory of Avempace by seeking to shape a rational knowledge of the divine. He develops the "id in me" in his « *Great commentary on Aristotle's De anima* », by designating the agent intellect separate and common to all humans, namely God, whom thinks and actualizes in the human mind the environment outside the body.

Still in Andalusia, largely influenced by his contemporaries Avicenna and Averroes, the eminent **Rabbi Moses Maimonides** (1138-1204) [8] also worked to reconcile the philosophy of Aristotle and science with the teachings of Judaism. He writes the *Mishe Torah*; publishes treatises in medicine and astronomy; and composed his main work the « *Guide to the Lost* » which is a treatise on theology and philosophy. However, Averroes' theory was not unanimously accepted, so Church doctor **Thomas Aquinas** (1225-1274) [9] whom wished to safeguard the principle of free will in the individuality of human thought, refuted in his « *Against Averroès* » the theory of the "id". This one remains in spite of the divergences and discussions aroused, founder of the field of psychology. The theological work of Thomas Aquinas based on the philosophy of Aristotle, marks Christianity by distinguishing faith (revealed theology) from reason (natural theology) in his presentation of the « *Summa theologica* ». The centuries that followed extended over a period of rivalry between currents of thought and orthodox religious. The philosophical and theological branches gradually detach themselves from each other and are organized into autonomous disciplines.

collection Mère du Livre, éditions Bod, Paris mars 2023 |
References : p.170-171.

[4] **Al-Ghazali** said Algazel | *Les intentions des philosophes (The intentions of philosophers)*.

[5] **Juda Halevi** « *Kuzari* » or *Livre de l'argumentation pour la défense de la religion méprisée (Book of Argument in Defense of Despised Religion)*.

[6] **Ibn Bajja** from his Latin name **Avempace** (primary works : *Lettre d'adieux ; Epître de la conjonction de l'intellect agent avec l'homme ; et Régime du solitaire.*)
| **Avempace** – *Farewell letter*.

[7] **Ibn Rochd** from his Latin name **Averroès** (main theological works: *Discours décisif ; Dévoilement et Incohérence de l'Incohérence*).

| **Averroès** – *L'intelligence et la pensée : Sur le De anima (Extensive commentary on Aristotle's De anima)* traduction from Latin by Alain de Libera, collection « GF », édition Flammarion, Paris 1998.

[8] **Moïse Maïmonide** – *Guide des égarés (Guide to the Lost)* (1190), traduction from Arabic by Salomon Munk (1856-1866), édition A.Franck, Paris 1856 – available on Archive.org in three volumes (1856-1870).

[9] **Thomas d'Aquin**, *Contre Averroès (De unitate intellectus contra Averroistas, 1270)* traduction from Latin by Alain de Libera, édition Flammarion, Paris 1994 (réimprimé en 1999).

| **Thomas d'Aquin**, *Somme théologique (Summa theologica)* (1266-1273), french traduction by A.M. Roguet, Tome 4, édition du Cerf, Paris 1984-1986.

| **Thomas d'Aquin**, *Commentaires des œuvres d'Aristote*,

Rational sciences, religions & theodicy

The era of the Renaissance and the Enlightenment marks a paradigm shift. Modern science, theology and modern philosophy are evolving and are now distinguished as disciplines in their own right. New perspectives opened up for theology when the German **Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz** (1646-1716) [10] published his « *Essays on Theodicy* », that the objective was to resolve the problem of the existence of evil in the plan of God. In the register of science, the first to mark the field of modern physics by integrating mathematical formulations into the description of the world, **Galileo** (1564-1642) [11] came up against theologians and supporters of Aristotle by developing methods science based on observation and experimentation. His contemporary, the Frenchman **René Descartes** (1596-1650) [12] developed in turn a universal method that he set thought in motion and organized scientific reasoning in his works. He illustrates his conception of the sciences in the image of a tree whose roots are metaphysics, physics the trunk, and branches all the other sciences reduced to three main ones: medicine; mechanics and the last degree of wisdom, morality.

At a time when the structuring of the scientific method was booming, the mathematician **Blaise Pascal** (1623-1662) [13] made a valuable contribution to the canon of scientific publications. He also writes his philosophical work in his « *Thoughts* » in which he identifies three orders: that of the body; of mind and heart. Strive to rank them under a higher order. He develops Christian theological paradoxes between faith and reason in the existence or not of God, identified as *Pascal's bet* for atheists, skeptics and free-thinkers. Another figure to mark the progress of knowledge,

[10] **Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz**, *Essais de Théodicée sur la bonté de Dieu, la liberté de l'homme et l'origine du mal* (*Theodicy essays on the goodness of God, the freedom of man and the origin of evil*) (1710).

[11] **Galilée**, *Sidereus Nuncius* (1610).

[12] **René Descartes**, *Règles pour la direction de l'esprit* (*Rules for the direction of the mind*) (1619-1620)
| **René Descartes**, *Discours de la méthode* (*Discourse on Method*) (1637).

[13] **Blaise Pascal**, *Pensées* (*Thoughts*) (1669). | Références : the three orders B.283, L.308 à B.793 ; *Pascal's bet*, fragment 397 | **Blaise Pascal** et **Louis Lafuma**, *Pensées* (1669), éditions Seuil 1962.

[14] **Charles Sanders Peirce**, *Le raisonnement et la logique des choses : les conférences de Cambridge* (*Reasoning and the Logic of Things: The Cambridge Lectures*) (1898), traduction by Christiane Chauviré, Pierre Thibaud & Claudine Tercekin, édition Cerf, Paris 1995.

| **Charles Sanders Peirce** (three volumes of his works edited by Claudine Tercekin & Pierre Thibaud aux éditions Cerf) :

Charles Sanders Peirce (1839-1914) [14], an American considered as particularly innovative in the conception of the theory of the investigation. He developed four methods including the scientific method which leads to reality by hypothesis. He develops pragmatism by adding the logic of abduction to the two phases of deduction and induction of empirical reasoning that he revisits. In his approach, he refutes the ontological metaphysics of yesteryear to the detriment of an analytical metaphysics that validates the first principles from which scientific investigations start.

More recently, the illustrious **Albert Einstein** (1879-1955) [15] published his theory of general Relativity in 1915 and established the mass-energy equivalence equation that made him famous, $E=mc^2$. Although recognized for his pure rational scientific positions, he also writes articles dealing with science and religion, a field which he claims himself, in his essay « *How I see the world* », from the pantheism of **Baruch Spinoza** (1632-1677) whom has banished from the Jewish community for heresy. In his « *Letter to God* » addressed to the philosopher **Eric Gutkind** (1877-1965), Einstein rejects traditional beliefs but does not qualify himself as atheist. His words refer to another of his contemporaries, the Austrian **Sigmund Freud** (1856-1939) [16] founder of modern psychoanalysis whom takes up the concept of the "id" as the unconsciousness of the three instances of the psychic apparatus (The ego, the id and the superego). The concept taken from the « *Book of the id* » written in the form of artificial correspondences imagined with Freud and published by the German psychoanalyst **Georg Groddeck** (1866-1934) [17], is a modern and organized evolution of the primary theory of the "id" by Averroes.

Pragmatisme et pragmatisme (2002) ; *Pragmatismes et sciences normatives* (2003) ; *Ecrits logiques* (2006).
| Référence : l'abduction, Manuscrit 692.

[15] **Albert Einstein**, *Comment je vois le monde* (*How i see the world*) (1934), collection "Champs Flammarion", édition Flammarion 1979.
| **Albert Einstein**, *Lettre à Dieu* (*Letter to God*), destinée à Éric Gutkind le 3 janvier 1954

| References of published articles:

– *Religion & science*, New York Times Magazine, 9 novembre 1930 ;
– *Science & religion I*, Adresse : Séminaire théologique de Princeton, 19 mai 1939 ;

– *Science & religion II*, Science, philosophie et religion, Symposium, 1941 ;

– *Religion & science : inconciliables ?* Le registre chrétien, juin 1948.

[16] **Sigmund Freud**, *Le Moi et le ça* (*The Me and the Id*) (1923), traduction de C.Baliteau, A.Bloch, J.M Rondeau. | Référence : Œuvres complètes de Freud/Psychanalyse, Tome XVI, Paris, PUF (Presses Universitaires de France), 1991. (Pages 255-301)

[17] **Georg Groddeck**, *Livre du ça* (*Book of the Id*) (1923), La République des Lettres, livre numérique.

In the West, the last contemporary years have also been the scene of many attempts to reconcile science and theology. **Pierre Teilhard de Chardin** (1881-1955) [18] a French Jesuit priest explores various scientific disciplines, and leads a personal theological approach not really appreciated in Christian circles. He takes up the theory of evolution of **Charles Darwin** (1809-1882), the biosphere of **Vernadsky** (1863-1945) that he unifies with Christian theodicy. In his theory, he places creation at an Alpha point of time and God at an Omega point that he describes as the Christ. Between both, the theory of evolution. He definitively ceased his research when the Holy See took offense at one of his publications on the subject of "original sin".

Another Frenchman, the doctor **Maurice Bucaille** (1920-1998) [19] tries a theological approach including the Quranic texts to the Biblical Scriptures in a context of progressive revelation. Wishing to demonstrate the conformity of the Quran to scientific theories, he nevertheless endeavored to point out the "inconsistencies" of the Bible not conform to the scientific knowledge of the time. That earned him criticism for his lack of objectivity. More recently, the award-winning American researcher **Ian Graeme Barbour** (1923-2013) [20] endeavors to link, through an approach that he describes subjective/objective, science and religion in his work « *Issues in Science and Religion* ». He makes comparisons between the language and methods of science and the language and methods of religion based on the Bible. His contemporary approach will have allowed the recognition of a domain of interaction between science and religion.

Despite the many figures and works that have marked the history of knowledge, this limited selection serves as an introduction to describe the autonomy and independence specific to the fields of science and religion. While ancient philosophy is defined by love and the search for knowledge and wisdom in many areas of knowledge, the division of disciplinary branches has taken place over time has ended up isolating each of both areas opposed in withdrawal and ignorance of the other. One wanting to be rational, the other spiritual. Ancient philosophy, which was once emancipatory from all forms of knowledge, has become for its part a diversity of currents of thought, dealing with various questions without developing its own methodology, except for the dissertation. Contemporary attempts to reconcile science and

theology have only resulted in transformation, criticism or comparison between these two fields.

A SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINE

Science is the sum of knowledge based on the principle of its acquisition by method and reflection. It has seen its development grow in the West as its argumentative and methodological techniques are organized around observation and experimentation. Its origin based on the natural sciences, established the object of its questions through the specialty of epistemology. The philosophical fragmentation that has taken place over the years has distinguished, without isolating them, the art of thought from the model of reasoning. However, Thinking and reasoning are characteristics naturally attributed to each one of the scientific and theological bodies in their respective areas of action. The methodical exploration of these common characteristics makes accessible the foundation of an exclusive median conciliation respecting the independence and autonomy specific to the two executive bodies, without disturbing their personal development. Far from being a simple field of interaction between science and theology, the creation of a median scientific discipline developing its own methodological approach would be able to make a contribution to the collective knowledge of humanity.

CONSTRUCTION OF NEOLOGISM

Then I started not without difficulty, the foundation of a discipline comprising its own methods and modes of reflection. To keep an intellectual independence far from the courses institutional schemes, based for the most part on limited academic achievements or inherited ideologies, I opted for self-taught. With all the independence that we lend to this mode of autonomous learning, the first difficulties appeared that ultimately make it its strength of character. In an institutionalized classic course whose paths are traced and framed, the doors have been ajar beforehand without even realizing it. While a self-taught course even conscientiously applied, has no recognized institutional value except that of the achievements it lent itself. As for the doors of

[18] **Pierre Teilhard de Chardin**, *Le phénomène humain (The human phenomenon)* (édition du Seuil, 1955), édition Points, Paris 2007.
| **Pierre Teilhard de Chardin**, *L'avenir de l'homme (The future of man)* (édition du Seuil, 1959), édition Points, Paris 2001.

[19] **Maurice Bucaille**, *La Bible, le Coran et la science : les Écritures Saintes examinées à la lumière des connaissances modernes (The Bible, the Koran and science: the Holy Scriptures examined in the light of modern knowledge)*, éditions Seghers, Paris 1976.

[20] **Ian G. Barbour**, *Issues in science and religion*, (English version) édition HarperCollins, 1971.

| **Ian G. Barbour**, *Quand la science rencontre la religion* (2000), Traduit de l'anglais (Etats-Unis) par Emmanuel Scavée, collection Transdisciplinarité, éditions du Rocher, 2005.

recognition, these remain closed until through perseverance, they are forced open.

Free thinking is what allowed the emergence of the first philosophies of observing nature. So remaining in control of my thought was the first act in the development of a new discipline that I named *eschapsology*. The root of this term is the etymological fusion of two preexisting specialties: *eschatology*, theological study of the end of time; and *collapsology* that is a multidisciplinary current studying the risks of a collapse of contemporary thermo-industrial civilization. This hybrid neologism was born from their common language consisting in the analysis of the causes and consequences of a collapse by domino effect. The etymology of the neologism *eschapsology* is composed by three parts. The first of comes from the Greek term [eschatos] translated as « last » in the state of mind of the discourse on the end of time; the second part of the Latin term [collapse] translating the fact of « collapse »; and in the third part the suffix [-logy] from the Greek “logos” to distinguish the analytical nature of the study. *Eschapsology* is a feminine gender word belonging to the grammatical category of nouns. The *eschapsologist* is the expert and specialist in this discipline.

THE SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO RESEARCH

To begin the construction of a median discipline that would maintain intellectual independence, reasoning objectivity and technical autonomy, I first had to determine the foundations of my scientific research approach (fig.1). The theoretical framework aims to study the theory of the Book, the principle consists in bringing together all the Holy Scriptures accepted by consensus, not to criticize them, denigrate them or compare them with each other or with science, but to place them in a context of progressive revelation. The Book is made up of the biblical texts in which are found in particular the Torah, the Psalms, the prophetic Corpus, the Gospel and the testimonies of the apostles and disciples; as well as the quranic revelation which includes the Quran and the authentic collections of the Sunnah. More recently discovered in 1947 buried in a Qumran cave near the Dead Sea, the Intertestamental Writings are leather scrolls that come between the Old Testament and the New Testament. All of these literatures form a library rich in ancient documents dating for some of them from the first time of writings. Once the concept of the Book has been organized into a theory, the intellectual approach consists of studying and analysing the texts in their original languages (Hebrew, Greek and Arabic), as well as the historical contexts of the revelations.

Fig.1 : Diagram of the scientific approach in eschapsology.

THE INTELLECTUAL PROGRESS BETWEEN SCIENCE AND THEOLOGY

The research methodology follows a process recognized by the scientific community. The steps and results of the research are presented in a continuum of two paradigms. Argumentative reasoning uses the three types of inferences abduction, deduction and induction, that stages are found in the first three fundamental works of the first Phase. This particularity's object of study to keep a theological intellectual essence thanks to the concept of the Book, while conscientiously applying the method of investigation in the research process, makes it an original concept of the middle of science and theology. The six volumes provided for by the literary collection of the first paradigm are divided into two phases, that the first of just completed, validates the primary stage of the foundation of the discipline.

My first discovery driving the research process, was the study of the meaning of the quranic expression [ahl al-kitab] that translates as «the People of [the] Book». The process applied to produce the immutable narratives of the Book organized into a theoretical concept proceeds by inspiration and revelation before being materialized in writing on a support. Conversely, the production of works of science evolves in space and time while remaining verifiable or refutable through the scientific method. The entire progress makes possible to affirm, verify, refute or question the theory.

The intellectual progress that takes place between the aspects of science and theology can be represented in the form of an organization chart (fig. 2). An interpretation in cohesion with the lexical field of the whole Book allows the discernment of its esoteric narrative. This very laborious step requires considerable time for data collection. It forms the theological aspect and allows new discoveries to be made without having recourse to any other literature than that of the Book. These new interpretations aim for a completely different understanding of the texts in order to extract a precise linguistic numerology from them, beginning the scientific aspect. To describe and predict the evolution of the studied system, eschapsology includes, not the mathematical tool recognized to bring precision to a theory particularly in physics, although not excluded from it, but the object of linguistic numerologies from the discernment. The linguistic numerology of the Book is not a simple operation of numerical calculation of letters or an extraction of numbers, as it has already been undertaken in the past, but a fine eloquence whose lexical accuracy is measured to the letter. The revised problem verse example, extracted from the Ineffable Letter a whole new model of physics at the end of the Phase (I).

Fig.2 : Flowchart of the intellectual progress between science and theology.

HYPOTHESIS, THE TRANSITION FROM THE COLLAPSE IN THE LIGHT OF THE BOOK

After bridging the gap between science and theology through the theoretical framework and the methodology, it remained to clarify the object of the approach by simply asking myself the right question: «*What am I looking for?* ». To translate the object of study into this central question, I already had to interpret the original verse that imposed the problem on this approach. How and by what power do we enter through the flow of the Heavens and the Earth as the Creator enjoins us to do in the reinterpreted verse : « *Ô tithé of djinns and men ! If you can enter through the flow of Heavens and Earth, then enter! But only enter by the sovereignty.* » [The All-Merciful 55:33]. The primary step of abduction is to formulate a new idea in the process of forming a hypothesis to solve the problem. The exploration is limited to the ten major signs of the end times. The literary work associated with this challenge [La Transition, de l'effondrement à la lumière du Livre (The Transition, from Collapse in the Light of the Book) – (fr) Bod edition, December 2020] relates the chronology of events from the point of collapse to the Hour of final gathering (fig.3). This reasoning forges a hypothetical narrative serving as an exploratory track to begin the empirical work. Once the point Ø of the collapse has been crossed, the chronology of events is irreversible, no turning back is possible. The ten great Signs follow one another in a systemic fall of the ecosystem.

The literature review [L'Ouverture, les deux réalités (The Opening, the two realities) – (fr) Bod edition, February 2021] is applied to the entire research process, as the intellectual tool forged to answer the question by involving the rational domain of science of matter. The theory according that two cosmoses (or two worlds) coexist was developed by great philosophers and scholars of yesteryear, in particular Plato with his theory of intelligible forms [1], in which divergences persist only in the way of approaching these two realities. The Opening determines two realities through the two major fields of physics, General Relative and Quantum Mechanics. Several laws are referenced, such as the law of entropy; the law of probability or the theory of Superstrings which unifies and translates the Heavens and the Earth according to dimensions. Other phenomena also appear such as gravitational waves and the celestial Table, cosmic object of wave-like symphonic compositions; the atom of faith, a macroscopic object that explains, among other things, the chain reaction of the respiratory mechanism introduced by fission during the first breath of life; or even the two types of consciousness, cerebral analytic and extraneuronal intuitive, which refer to two perceptions of the world.

The unification of the two realities is done through the perception of the two physical systems. The soul resides in cognition and forms the *Analytical Brain Consciousness* (CAC) which connects us to the Earth through the four dimensions of space-time. The Spirit sits in the organ of the heart and forms the *Intuitive Extraneuronal Consciousness* (CIE) which connects us to the seven Heavens superimposed on the vertical scale of celestial time. The soul (analytical consciousness) and the Spirit (intuitive consciousness), are independent of each other, just like the two great fields of physics, but evolve in a complementary way. The fifth dimension is represented in the Book by the first Heaven. It allows the both consciousnesses to overlap and merge into each other. The vibratos of the Superstrings are produced by the *Celestial Table*. String theory and M-theory structure the whole Earth and the seven Heavens in eleven dimensions in which: the first four dimensions represent worldly space and time; the fifth forms the interval between the two realities; and beyond, the next five dimensions are only accessible through the *atom of faith*. Other discoveries decay the atom of faith as an object leading to quantum dimensions through the first Heaven.

Fig.3 : Hypothetical representation of the period of collapse in the light of the Book.

The realization of a mental experiment composed of two observers that we schematize in the form of a chart (fig.4), represents the displacements through space-time and celestial-time. One of the observers placed on the horizontal x-axis is directed from the past towards the future, so that he discovers the course of

events only as the arrow of time evolves in the present. This worldly position, with its back to the abscissa axis, gives it the cognitive particularity of storing the memory of events, once they have passed. Its movements take place according to the matter (body envelope) maintained by the earth's gravity. The second observer placed at the top of the y-axis, is directed face down so that he is privileged to see all the events simultaneously on the entire vertical scale. The vision of each of the two observers plays an important role in the way they process information. The sense of vision, whether cognitive or intuitive, is related to eyesight of that the eye is the organ of perception. The wave-particle duality highlighted by Young's famous slit experiment applies here according to its own principle of duality.

Fig.5 : The both observers apply the principle of wave-particle duality.

Fig.4 : Graph of horizontal and vertical time scales.

Each observer reflects one of the two concepts of wave and corpuscle. They are inseparable from each other, like the two complementary eyes of a single look directed in the same direction (fig.5). The information received by the organic eye is emitted by electromagnetic waves, in particular the visible light spectrum, but also the variations of other frequency fields perceptible through the various measuring devices. While the quantum eye fixes its observation on the corpuscles, which has the consequence of interfering with the wave diffraction through the probability curve. Each of the time scales converge to superimpose each other like the two eyes of a single look.

EXPERIMENT THROUGH THE TESTIMONY OF MEMORIES OF WISDOM

Science describes the principles, mechanisms and phenomena that govern the functioning of the universe. It provides a physical answer to the how of existence that it sometimes predicts by introducing mathematical equations, but which nevertheless remain limited to a theoretical conception. To fill this gap, it uses the experimental method, particularly in physics, chemistry or biology, whose rigor in the process leads to an understanding of the phenomenon or object studied. Following this principle, the induction step describes the experimentation of achieving the median intellectual process. Since science, unlike theology, is based on evidence and not on beliefs, Testimony [*Témoignage, les mémoires de Sagesse (Testimony, the memoirs of Wisdom)* - (fr) Bod edition, March 2023] focuses research on the precise phenomenon of the first Heaven, i.e. the fifth dimension. The collection of memoirs shed light on the Holy Spirit from Named Wisdom as an individual person. Many theological discoveries emerged from this exploration, including the Libra method included in the Book; the first story of Life; the allegory of the Body of Christ and the Assembly which composes its members and ministries; as well as the description of the elements that found the Kingdom of God (fig.6). In the same register, the approach of Pierre Teilhard de Chardin places creation at an Alpha point of time and God at an Omega point which he describes as being Christ. However, this remains devoid of a fundamental scientific method, merely substituting scientific language to graft it onto biblical language.

The writing of the Memoirs of Wisdom brings to the whole of the research a more solid structure of the foundations. It plunges the reader into the heart of the lexical field of the Book. The object of the Book is a material compilation of ancient papyrus written in chronological times diverging one another. These Texts raised as a Saint rank by the theological corps, include the celestial Book described as a Spirit coming from the Order in opposition to the worldly material Book. Ancient relics are material evidence of the writings of

their authors. The proof that the experimentation of a conjuncture did indeed take place on Earth in a future time is contained in the discernment of the Book. In the 90s, the famous theoretical physicist and cosmologist **Stephen Hawking** (1942-2018) tried to prove by a whole series of calculations that no time loop allowing travel in the past could exist other than by elementary particles. He also conducted major work on black holes that results will remain valuable to science. His conclusions on the time travel of matter are clear: the reason he cites to describe its impossibility is that we are not invaded by hordes of travelers from the future. However, experimentation through the study of the *Memoirs of Wisdom* finds two concepts: one, describes the phenomenon of displacement of the Holy Spirit via the fifth dimension; the other, the phenomenon of the displacement of matter through a time loop brought to light by the first story of Life.

Fig.6 : Synthetic figure representing the extent of the "Kingdom of God" according to the theory of the Book, revealing "the Arch" which is the celestial vault delimiting the first sky according to a temporal and not spatial astronomy.

MODELING RESULTS

THE KEY TO SCIENCE

Essential phase at the base of this scientific approach, the construction of a physical model is the crucial step which tends to reproduce the phenomenon to be studied making possible to dissociate the imagination from the concretization of knowledge (fig.7). The results of the work model filter dripping occurring in the fifth dimension into a stretched perspective between Earth and Heavens. Beyond, the standard representations of the grid structure of space-time. The idea of the four dimensions is schematized under the aspect of a earth sphere. Projected in time like the shadow of the globe, the Transition period forms the intermediate period which leads to Heaven. The point $\emptyset$ marks the beginning of the collapse, i.e. the horizon of events which once crossed, makes any backtracking impossible. The events follow one another until reaching the Day of Judgment marking the end of the transition. Then, begins the Day of Resurrection for a period of a thousand years. The first resurrected creatures are inevitably drawn to the center of gravity that is at the gathering place. The configuration of this region of spacetime fixes the gravitational Singularity in space and time. Stretched behind the transition like the extension of a temporal bridge so narrow that it can only be crossed gradually, corpuscle after corpuscle, in which case it would close in on whoever else tried to enter. The model borrowed from the elegant geometry of the Morris-Thorne wormhole, offers broad geodesic properties allowing interesting trajectories in accordance with the science of the Book.

The event horizon reaches the gravitational singularity at a temporal point, marking the conjunction of the fundamental interactions achieved in the mid-dimension. During the flow through this singularity occurs the rebound of an oscillation of the curvature of space-time which indefinitely regenerates the cycle of Life from one end of the Earth to the other. Like are perpetuated the cycles that balance the entire terrestrial and cosmic ecosystem.

The classic simplification of the object of a wormhole consists of marking two opposite points A and B on a sheet of paper, then bending it until the two points connect and get possible to cross the sheet from one point to another with the pencil. This conception, which implies a geometric shortcut between two regions of space-time, nevertheless denies a return to the past. Standard representations of time refer to an observer constantly frozen in space who only enters movement for brief moments mathematically superimposed on each other. Eschapsology, in its scientific approach, completes the collective knowledge of humanity with the key to science from the Book. This

introduces a fifth dimension belonging to a celestial-time that overhangs all the moments in a single time. Four-dimensional space-time defines the time taken by electromagnetic waves to reach the cognitive view from the distant cosmos, while celestial-time added with fifth

dimension describes the wavering emitted from the point $\emptyset$ of time originates of the intuitive view.

Ouafae Lamraoui.

Fig.7 : Modeling (in two dimensions) of the flow of the Earth and Heavens.

ARTICLE REFERENCES

Publication date : 25 Août 2023
Scientific discipline : Eschapsology
Article : Eschapsology : Synthesis of the emergence of a middle discipline between science and theology.
Version : English
Author : Ouafae Lamraoui
DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.8280640